

Enzyme-receptor duality and multimodality

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Running title: Enzyme-receptor duality and multimodality

Keywords: enzyme, receptor, enzyme-receptor duality, enzyme-receptor multimodality, allosteric modulator, noncompetitive inhibitor, enzyme-activity modifying factor,

Receptors can exhibit promiscuity, duality and multimodality with respect to the sensed molecule (ligand) and/or factor being sensed. Some receptors may exhibit duality in function. For example, VEGFR2 is a receptor as it is a tyrosine kinase whose activity is regulated either via VEGF binding or HS- anion interaction at sites other than the catalytic domain. Likewise with respect to sensing role, enzyme can also exhibit duality as receptor. Again with the VEGFR2 example, we can say VEGFR2 is an enzyme that acts as a receptor that senses VEGF and HS- anion. However, it is unclear whether the catalytic domain of the enzymes can also be used as a ligand sensing domain. If the enzyme's catalytic activity can be reduced or stopped, but the enzyme's catalytic domain can still be used as a ligand-sensing domain, then the enzyme can now potentially act as a receptor, provided it interacts with a signal transducer and initiates a signaling event. Thus, for an enzyme to exhibit duality as a receptor (other than receptor-linked enzymes, metalloproteins, sonoproteins, photoproteins, and thermoproteins). The following must occur: Other molecules (e.g., non-competitive inhibitor, allosteric modulator, enzyme-activity modifying factors) must bind to an enzyme at a site other than the catalytic site. The binding must induce a structural change in the enzyme's catalytic site allowing the enzyme to bind the substrate (ligand) but not act on it. In addition, either the bound molecule must act as a signal transducer or an additional signal transducer must bind or unbind the enzyme and initiate a signaling event. Moreover, if the enzyme can form dimers (or polymers), then one monomer of the enzyme can act as a receptor while the other monomer can potentially act as signal transducer, provided that the ligand binding in the first monomer can regulate the activity of the other monomers. Finally, another form of duality could be that enzyme-linked receptors can potentially switch their role. The catalytic domain becomes the ligand sensing domain, while the ligand sensing domain becomes the catalytic domain.

DISCLOSURE

The funding agency and institution S.A. is affiliated with was not involved in the contents of the manuscript. The author used DeepL Write to correct the English language and takes full responsibility for the manuscript.

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